

Modified Walkley-Black method for the determination of Total Organic Carbon (TOC) in ferrous iron rich rock samples and its correlation with Loss-on-Ignition (LOI)

Prithwish Chakraborty, Adarsh Kumar, A. K. Jain and R. Lalithambal

Chemistry Laboratory, Atomic Minerals Directorate for Exploration and Research,
Department of Atomic Energy, Northern Region, New Delhi-110 066, India

Abstract : A modified Walkley-Black (WB) volumetric method for the determination of Total Organic Carbon (TOC) in ferrous rich rock samples has been developed. High amount of ferrous being an interferent in the determination of TOC needs to be removed. The removal of ferrous was carried out using hydrofluoric acid treatment followed by TOC determination by Walkley-Black method. In the present study, the temperature profiling using Muffle furnace was carried out to ascertain the loss of organic matter by combustion and correlate the TOC values as obtained by modified Walkley-Black method. This combustion technique and the modified method was applied on black shale samples obtained from Loharka, Dehardun area and few synthetic samples rich in ferrous ions. Study regarding temperature profile of high ferrous and black shale samples done by a temperature controlled Muffle furnace, suggests that, the fraction of weight loss between 450 to 500 °C corresponds to the TOC values. The values obtained by both the methods were in good agreement with the values obtained from TOC analyser.

Keywords : Total Organic Carbon, Walkley-Black method, black shale samples.

Introduction

The exact determination and characterization of organic and inorganic carbon (OC and IC, respectively) in solid samples is one of the most extensively performed analyses in geological studies and of growing importance in the environmental field. Important characteristics of the organic matter include their ability to form water-soluble and water insoluble complexes with metal ions which can affect the physical and chemical properties of the affected metal¹⁻³; interact with clay minerals and bind particles together; sorb and desorb both naturally-occurring and anthropogenically-introduced organic compounds; absorb and release plant nutrients; and hold water in the soil environment. As a result of these characteristics, the determination of total organic carbon is an essential part of any site characterization since its presence or absence can markedly influence how chemicals will react. Inorganic reactions on natural uranium ore deposits can produce redox states of +4 and +6, which have dramatically different geochemical properties^{1,4}. Uranium(IV)

generally exists as an insoluble oxide, although it can be complexed with various ligands including natural organic matter. Uranium(VI), however, is soluble in natural waters as the uranyl ion and has an extensive complexation chemistry with inorganic and organic moieties⁵⁻⁸. TOC is very important to understand the geo-chemistry of an area, the presence of organic carbon suggests reducing environment of the area, mobility of different elements including uranium gets restricted and may form a secondary deposit because of the reducing environment. TOC contents may be used qualitatively to assess the nature of the sampling location (e.g. was a depositional area) or may be used to normalize portions of the analytical chemistry data set (e.g. equilibrium partitioning).

The Walkley-Black (WB) volumetric method⁹ is one of the classical methods for rapid analysis of organic carbon (OC) in soils and sediments. The method is based on the oxidation of organic matter by potassium dichromate (K₂Cr₂O₇)-sulfuric acid mixture followed by back titration of the excessive dichromate by ferrous ammonium

sulfate ($\text{Fe}(\text{NH}_4)_2(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$). The method is widely used for OC analysis. Ferrous iron, if present, leads to high results for the dichromate-ferrous sulphate titration and require 1 or 2 days air-dried to remove ferrous interference. In the present paper authors have modified Walkley-Black method for removal of ferrous interference and also a rapid TOC determination method has been suggested on the basis of weight loss with temperature.

Experimental

Reagents : 1 N Potassium dichromate, 0.5 N ferrous ammonium sulphate, sodium fluoride (NaF), diphenylamine : $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHC}_6\text{H}_5$, were prepared as per procedure described elsewhere¹⁰, using AR/AnalaR/GR grade chemicals. Sulphuric acid 98%, phosphoric acid 85% were used as such.

Ferriin indicator was prepared by dissolving 1.485 g, *o*-phenanthroline monohydrate and 0.695 g ferrous sulphate in approximately 80 mL deionised water, then dilute to 100 mL and preserved in dark bottle away from light.

Procedure :

Walkley-Black method : Weigh accurately 0.2–0.5 g (200 mesh) dried sample in 500 mL conical flask. Accurately add 10 mL 1 N $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ and swirl the flask gently to disperse the sample in the solution. Add 20 mL concentrated H_2SO_4 . Immediately swirl the flask until the sample and the reagent are mixed. Set aside to cool slowly on an asbestos sheet in a fume cupboard. Two blanks (without sample) must be run in the same way to standardize the $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution. When cool (20–30 min), dilute to 200 mL with deionised water. Add 10 ml phosphoric acid and 0.2 g sodium fluoride. Proceed with the $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution titration using either the “ferriin” indicator or barium diphenyl sulphate indicator.

Modified Walkley-Black method for Fe^{2+} rich samples : 0.5 g sample was taken in a Teflon beaker. 5 ml HF was added to the sample and was evaporated to dryness on hot plate. The dried sample was then taken for TOC determination as given in method A.

Temperature profiling : 0.5 g sample was taken in a platinum crucible covered with platinum lid and was heated

150 °C, 200 °C, 300 °C, 400 °C, 450 °C, 500 °C, 550 °C, 600 °C, 700 °C, 800 °C in a Muffle furnace for 90 min at each temperature. Loss in weight was measured at each temperature intervals.

Results and discussion

Modified Walkley-Black method for Fe^{2+} rich samples :

When this technique is utilised in Fe^{2+} rich samples such as pyrite, it is found that the interference is positive in nature, this is because, in case of Fe^{2+} rich samples the consumption of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ is not only because of the OM but also by the Fe^{2+} (excess) present in the sample. Therefore a pre-separation of Fe^{2+} was required before analysis of TOC by WB method. It was found that a single treatment to the sample by HF was enough to get rid of Fe^{2+} upto around 98% (Table 4). The HF treatment opens up the matrix and Fe^{2+} present gets converted to Fe^{3+} by air oxidation. The same treated sample was then taken up for TOC determination. Black shale samples obtained from Loharka, Dehradun area were having OM ranging from 3–6% where as the ferrous content was less than 4%, therefore, to study the effect of excess Fe^{2+} the known amount of ferrous was added and TOC was determined by the proposed method (Table 1B).

The results by Walkley-Black method, modified Walkley-Black method (in which the samples are air-dried for 1 or 2 days contain insignificant amounts of soluble iron compounds) and TOC analyzer are compiled (Table 1A). From the Table 1A it can be inferred that ferrous

Table 1A. Comparison of TOC values by Walkley-Black method, modified Walkley-Black method and TOC analyzer of black shale samples

Sl. no.	Sample no.	%Fe(II)	%TOC by WBM	%TOC by modified WBM	%TOC by TOC analyser
1.	AMD-1	0.85	2.62	2.54	2.50
2.	AMD-2	1.56	3.65	3.42	3.46
3.	AMD-3	2.24	3.23	3.10	3.20
4.	AMD-4	4.62	3.56	3.02	2.99
5.	AMD-5	6.85	4.23	3.55	3.46
6.	AMD-11	8.05	5.42	4.25	4.10
7.	AMD-12	7.66	4.63	4.30	4.25

Table 1B. Comparison of TOC values by Walkley-Black method, modified Walkley-Black method and TOC analyzer in ferrous rich synthetic samples

Sl. no.	Sample no.	%Fe(II)	%TOC by WBM	%TOC by modified WBM	%TOC by TOC analyser
1.	AMD-6	8.23	4.18	3.50	3.48
2.	AMD-7	9.59	6.45	5.36	5.45
3.	AMD-8	11.07	6.92	5.76	5.86
4.	AMD-9	13.43	8.89	7.21	7.38
5.	AMD-10	16.81	8.80	7.09	7.11

rectly be determined for TOC by conventional Walkley-Black method as there was no significant contribution of ferrous in the titer value up to that level (Table 1).

Validation :

The black shale samples from the Dehradun area were analysed using Walkley-Black method. In case of ferrous rich samples, modified Walkley-Black method was applied. The method was also utilised for the determination of TOC in few synthetic samples. These samples were also analysed by TOC analyzer and values obtained were

Table 2. Temperature profile (i.e. weight loss with temperature)

Sl. no.	Sample no.	% TOC	Temperature (°C)										%TOC (Weight loss at 450 °C and 500 °C)
			150	200	300	400	450	500	550	600	700	800	
1.	AMD-4	2.99	0.71	<0.05	1.21	<0.05	2.30	0.56	<0.05	0.42	0.33	0.56	2.86
2.	AMD-5	3.46	0.41	<0.05	1.30	0.70	3.01	0.53	0.13	0.86	0.26	0.90	3.54
3.	AMD-6	3.48	0.41	<0.05	2.02	1.20	2.85	0.57	0.25	0.54	0.92	1.20	3.42
4.	AMD-7	5.45	0.32	<0.05	2.01	1.60	4.26	1.29	0.23	0.61	1.32	1.45	5.55
5.	AMD-8	5.86	0.42	<0.05	3.63	1.50	4.80	1.13	0.16	0.92	1.45	1.63	5.93
6.	AMD-9	7.32	0.16	<0.05	0.52	0.30	5.95	1.20	0.38	1.01	2.01	2.11	7.15
7.	AMD-10	7.11	0.62	<0.05	1.40	0.30	5.86	1.10	0.29	1.03	2.16	1.87	6.96

below 4% can directly be determined for TOC by conventional Walkley-Black method as there was no significant contribution of ferrous in the titer value up to that level, whereas, sample containing ferrous higher than 4% must be separated.

Temperature profiling :

It was found that the loss in weight at 150 °C corresponds to the moisture content of the sample. Then at every 50 °C interval, after heating for 1 ½ h, the weight of the sample was measured. It was seen that upto 400 °C no significant loss was obtained. The fraction loss between 400 °C to 500 °C corresponds to the TOC values obtained by modified WB method. Therefore it can be suggested that the TOC of black shales samples can also be determined using muffle furnace by calculating weight loss between 450–500 °C (Table 2). Heating at up to 500 °C ferrous ion does not significantly get oxidised to ferric and therefore, there is negligible contribution from ferrous ions in terms of weight gain. It was observed that the samples containing ferrous from 6.85 to 16.81% weight gain is merely 0.05 to 0.30% (Table 3). It was also observed that samples containing ferrous below 4% can di-

Table 3. Gain in ferrous rich samples at 500 °C

S. no.	Sample no.	%Fe(II)	%Wt. loss at 500 °C	%Wt. gain at 500 °C
1.	AMD-5	6.85	0.41	0.05
2.	AMD-6	8.23	0.41	0.06
3.	AMD-7	9.59	0.32	0.12
4.	AMD-8	11.07	0.42	0.18
5.	AMD-9	13.43	0.16	0.20
6.	AMD-10	16.81	0.62	0.30

Table 4. Determination of ferrous before and after removal

S. no.	Sample no.	%Fe(II) Before removal	%Fe(II) After removal (by HF treatment)
1.	AMD-1	0.85	0.05
2.	AMD-2	1.56	0.05
3.	AMD-3	2.24	0.05
4.	AMD-4	4.62	0.05
5.	AMD-5	6.85	0.15
6.	AMD-6	8.23	0.25
7.	AMD-7	9.59	0.25
8.	AMD-8	11.07	0.45
9.	AMD-9	13.43	1.20
10.	AMD-10	16.81	1.35

in good agreement. The fraction of loss in weight between 450–500 °C also gave nearly complete (~95%) recovery of TOC.

Conclusion

The modified Walkley-Black method is specially designed for the samples having high ferrous content, in the absence of TOC analyzer in a laboratory this method can very well utilised for rock samples containing high ferrous content. The method was utilised for the determination of TOC in the black shale samples and few synthetic samples. The values obtained was in good agreement with that of TOC analyzer. Study regarding temperature profile of high ferrous and black shale samples done by a temperature controlled Muffle furnace, suggests that, the fraction of weight loss between 450 to 500 °C corresponds the TOC values obtained by modified WB method and that of TOC analyzer. The proposed method is rapid and very useful for routine analysis of TOC.

References

1. D. Langmuir, "Aqueous Environmental Geochemistry", Prentice-Hall, Inc., Upper Saddle River, NJ, 1997.
2. K. G. J. Nierop, B. Jansen and J. M. Verstraten, *Sci. Total Environ.*, 2002, **300**, 201.
3. D. Schmitt, H. E. Taylor, G. R. Aiken, D. A. Roth and F. H. Frimmel, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2002, **36**, 2932.
4. I. Casas, J. de Pablo, J. Gimenez, M. E. Torrero, J. Bruno, E. Cera, R. J. Finch and R. C. Eging, *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta*, 1998, **62**, 2223.
5. K. R. Czerwinski, G. Buckau, F. Scherbaum and J. L. Kim, *Radiochim. Acta*, 1994, **65**, 111.
6. J. J. Lenhart and B. D. Honeyman, *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta*, 1999, **63**, 2891.
7. M. L. Pacheco and J. Havel, *J. Radioanal. Nucl. Chem.*, 2001, **248**, 565.
8. B. P. Jackson, J. F. Ranville, P. M. Bertsch and A. G. Sowder, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2005, **39**, 2478.
9. A. Walkley and I. A. Black, *Soil Sci.*, 1934, **37**, 29; A. Walkley, *Soil Sci.*, 1947, **63**, 251.
10. A. I. Vogel, "Textbook of Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 6th ed., Pearson Education.